

In this document we reply to the comments by the editor and reviewers. The main points of the reviewers were to reduce the jargon and requirements for pre-existing knowledge, explain all concepts more clearly, restructure parts of the manuscript, improve and add figures and add more information about how Figure 1 was created, and a large number of smaller comments. We have addressed all points raised, and incorporated changes related to the points below. We believe the feedback has improved our manuscript, and hope you are as positive about the revised manuscript as we are. Comments from reviewers and editors are in normal font, our responses are in bold.

Reviewer 1

1. I recommend noting the intended audience early in the article (is it toxicologists and environmental health researchers new to open science?). What might they gain after reading this paper? What are your goals and how can this paper uniquely help readers achieve those goals relative to other metascientific papers? Be explicit here. The field is toxicology, so also briefly mentioning the state of affairs here and how your claims and help are needed. Connect more to toxicology somewhere in the first few pages.

Response: We tried our best to engage the specific audience of the journal by providing relevant examples. These can be found in lines 150-151, 177, 250-252, 349-350, 492-493, 838-839, 923-935 of the manuscript. As we state in the article, our goal is to provide a state of the art review of the benefits, criticisms, and some practical aspects related to preregistration and registered reports.

3.A Line 466: You stated here, “This correlational study cannot tell us why more null results appear in the literature”. While the study self may not be able to do this, I would, however assume that it can be hypothesized that the presence of the “in practice acceptance” given by the RR format would push researchers to be less prone to cherry picking and selective reporting. Also, knowing that their protocol might be more prone to scrutiny could amplify this behaviour, I guess? (You somewhat mention it later in the text, but not with these terms exactly).

Response: We think it is important to not draw causal inferences from correlational data, but we agree that the hypothesis raised by the reviewer is very plausible. In line with the reviewer's comment, we now note that it is plausible that after receiving the “in-principle acceptance” given by Registered Reports, researchers are less prone to p-hacking and cherry picking. To make it more explicit, we have introduced minor changes and added the following sentence: “In fact, it seems plausible that researchers are less prone to *p*-hacking and cherry picking after obtaining “in-principle acceptance” for their Registered Reports.” Now it can be read as follows (line 545): “This correlational study cannot tell us why more null results appear in the literature. One reason could be that researchers might primarily use Registered Reports when they have a high prior they will observe a null effect. A second reason could be that, with all things equal, without systematic bias much less than 96% of hypothesis tests would yield statistically significant results (Scheel et al., 2021). In fact, it seems plausible that researchers are less prone to p-hacking and cherry picking after obtaining “in-principle acceptance” for their Registered Reports.”.

3. B. Moreover, do you know if this is something that any mixed-research studies have looked into/have tested? There are a few qualitative studies in the biomedical field about the

potential use of registries, but they do not target RRs specifically (e.g. Wieschowski et al., 2016 and 2020).

Response: After considering the two qualitative papers suggested by the reviewer, and searching the literature, we do not believe there are any mixed-methods studies addressing this arguably very interesting question concerning if Registered Reports make people feel less pressure to give in to systematic bias. The two studies suggested by the reviewer did not target RR but study registries. We have heard anecdotal evidence supporting the reviewer's hypothesis but do not know of any research on this question.

4. In the section “Metascientific evaluations of preregistration and Registered Reports”, the part about preregistration seems a bit less developed than the part about registered reports, notably about the positive effect that study registry can have (according to the literature). A study like the one of Kaplan & Irvin (2015) on how registries increased the reporting of null outcomes in clinical trials could be relevant.

Response: Thanks for suggesting this study, which we knew about, but had not cited. As suggested by the reviewer, we have included and discussed Kaplan and Irvin's study. However, we do note the study does not allow us to claim registries *increased* the reporting of null outcomes (plausible as that claim might be). Now it can be read as: “This improved transparency is often regarded as one of the positive aspects of preregistration (Spitzer & Mueller, 2023; Toth et al., 2021) and clinical registries (Kaplan & Irvin, 2015). For instance, Kaplan & Irvin (2015) compared the proportion of clinical trials showing a benefit of the intervention before and after the imposition that clinical trials had to be registered in year 2000. They observed that before 2000, 17 of 20 trials (57%) showed a benefit of the intervention in comparison to only 2 of 25 trials (8%) after 2000. Although this result suggests that the proportion of positive results in trials declined after 2000, we cannot make any causal claim from the observed results as it was a retrospective observational study which only included a small number of trials (n = 55), and unmeasured confounders could have impacted the observed results”.

5. Could you contrast falsificationism with its counterpart verificationism (<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Verificationism>)? I believe that is how science has been operating in practice, right?

Response: We would like to point out that there is a distinction between verificationism and what researchers usually do which is to confirm their hypotheses by affirming the consequent, which follows: If the hypothesis is true, an observation should occur (A then B); we observe B; therefore, A is true. This is a logical fallacy known as modus ponens. Verificationism, on the other hand (as in the link by the reviewer) is a philosophy of science central to logical positivism about which statements are meaningful, and which not.

How science has been operating in practice is, we believe, best captured by a lack of severe tests. These make it too easy for researchers to support their predictions, when these predictions are wrong. Our revisions (line 309) hopefully make the importance of the idea of severe tests much clearer.

Considering the above, and to address the reviewer's comment, we have added the following information regarding falsificationism (lines 309-312): “Both preregistration and Registered Reports are practices that are aligned with methodological falsificationism in the sense that they formalize procedures that make it harder for researchers to prove their hypotheses right when they are actually wrong. This increases the falsifiability of predictions.”

6. Regarding the term "biasing selection effects," it is similar to "selection bias." So there is some potential for some readers to mistake the two when learning of both of them. Can you distinguish these in the body of the article from selection bias and selective reporting bias? Here, thoughtful consideration of readers' existing knowledge like HARKing is key. A nested set (Venn/Euler) diagram visualizing the connections between biases could be useful.

Response: Upon reflection, we agree the term 'biasing selection effects' (used by Mayo, 2018) was not the most intuitively understandable terminology to use. We have changed this into 'systematic bias' which we believe is clearer and more widely used. We have also more clearly indicated that selective reporting and publication bias are examples of systematic bias, and now write "Systematic bias can occur throughout the research process, for example when deciding which alternative theories to test, which measures to use, which statistical tests to report (i.e., selective reporting), or which studies to submit to scientific journals (i.e., publication bias)." We believe this is a sufficient solution, and no diagram is needed.

7. Lns 260-64. "researchers, who test hypotheses from a methodological falsificationist approach to science should preregister their studies if they want a science that has intersubjectively established severely tested claims." What should non-falsificationists or severe testers do? Any arguments for them to adopt preregistration? Potentially missing an appeal to many scholars here. One cannot expect that all readers will support a severe testing approach to statistics. Around line 600, you mention compatibility with some forms of Bayesian statistics. That could be repeated here briefly and also unpacked for the reader in a few sentences to describe the compatibility with Bayesian statistics.

Response: Due to comments from both reviewers our manuscript has been significantly restructured, so this section now features in 'Is preregistration worth the effort?', lines 640 and further. While we emphasised that hypothesis testing must imply severe testing to reduce as much as possible the chance of making incorrect claims, we also noted that exploratory research and research with accessible secondary data do not test a hypothesis, therefore do not need to be preregistered. So, researchers who do not want to perform severe tests should perform exploratory research, which is also very important. We extensively discuss exploratory research in the section on unintended side-effects. This distinction applies to the same extent to Bayesian statistics, which can also focus on either testing, or exploration.

8. Lns 274-77: I agree with your basic caution of the goal of preregistration, though where would the open lab notebook live? Github? OSF, Figshare, and Zenodo? Can't the preregistration platform work as an open lab notebook for qualitative researchers? There is a pragmatic use of preregistration ****platforms**** for exploratory and qualitative research (fast and easy to get started and join the broader open science community with shared tools). Or do you advise using/creating other tools for open lab notebooks? Clarifying this could help. Multiple people could use the same platform for different purposes, right?

Response: Although the length of the manuscript only allows us to add a short statement about this important topic, this comment is incorporated in lines 328-333 as follows: " Features of platforms such as GitHub (Scroggie et al., 2023) and Zenodo (Schapira et al., 2019) make them ideal tools to host these open lab notebooks. These free and open-access platforms allow users to track all the information about who did what and when, thereby allowing higher transparency and real-time sharing of any changes to the planning, as well as promoting the moral nature of open science." Not that a very small subset of researchers has used the Open Science Framework as a lab notebook, making up to 20 versions of a preregistration. However, this is

incredibly costly for the OSF as each version of a preregistered project needs to be stored for 50 years. It is much more efficient to use git to store a time-stamped text file with changes.

9. Figure 1 / Line 184: You mention the identification of 18 surveys here. Although it is not the article's main topic, it would be interesting to know how they were identified and if your approach was systematic (i.e., try to get all surveys) or closer to a scoping technique. If this work was published elsewhere/made available elsewhere, I would recommend referring to it. Otherwise, you may consider providing more information on the identification method and methodological details in the supplementary materials. You now provide an OSF project within which you have the code for analysis, but the identification methods are not mentioned.

Response: Supplementary materials were revised to contain information regarding the sampling method and details of the surveys used by each study. We believe these are all studies on this topic to date. This table has not been published elsewhere, and this note has also been explicitly mentioned in the supplementary materials. It now reads:

" Figure 1 in the main manuscript depicts the proportion of researchers and students in diverse fields who admit to having engaged in systematic bias practices at least once. The papers were identified through back-citation in a literature review, as all cited the original study by John et al. (2012), and by sharing an earlier version of the Figure on social media and asking for any missing studies that could be included. This graph was specifically prepared for this study and has not been published elsewhere, but it is also included in a free online open textbook https://lakens.github.io/statistical_inferences/. Table 1 provides information on the questionnaires and samples of each paper included in the graph. Tabel 2 below provides examples of items."

10. Figure 1 / Line 185: you state here that the surveys looked at a similar set of questions; is there any way for these surveys to be fully accessible? Or give further explanation on how the categorisation was made? For instance, I was quite surprised that there are two categories for "selectively reporting what worked" and "selective reporting outcomes" , as I would believe these two to be closely linked. Is this how the survey defined each category? Once again, I realise this is not the main focus of this study, but some additional information in supplementary materials would be appreciated.

Response: Information regarding the categorization has been added to the supplementary materials. Another table has been created to connect the labels used on the figure with the respective items in the questionnaire, and examples of labels used by the original study by John et al. (2012). It now reads:

" Nine of the twelve categories presented here are the same as those defined by John et al. (2012) [including selectively reporting what worked and selective reporting outcomes]. Their last category (i.e., Falsifying data) was removed from our representation due to its different nature compared to the other practices presented here (Falsifying data constitutes research misconduct, whereas the others are biasing selection practices). Three additional categories (i.e., Selectively reporting performed analyses, Selectively including covariates, and Switching analysis selectively) were added because five or more studies had reported self-admission rates for these practices, which share the same nature as the biasing selection practices identified by

John et al. (2012). Table 2 presents a sample question from the surveys used by previous researchers and the labels used by John et al. (2012) and by our team in Figure 1 to refer to them. "

11. Figure 1: summarizes the prevalence of researchers admitting to conducting research 195 practices that reduce the severity of tests. I definitely want Figure 1 included, as it provides a needed synthesis of the literature. However, it must be redesigned and reprogrammed for clarity. I find Wilke's Fundamentals of Data Visualisation helpful (Wilke 2019), esp. especially chapter 21 on multi-panel figures (color and visualizing amounts). Multi-colored bars for small multiples plots like this are not advisable due to the sensory complexity of it. The data are readable after a while, but consider revising the plot such that:

A. The title is a bit larger (20-50%) for readability and mention the time frame (at least once in their life? month? year?) This is to ensure that skimmers can glean the information easily and accurately.

B. y-axis labels are presented horizontally. It might be useful to place them at the top of each subplot as a title in sentence-case form. Reading vertical text is difficult. Avoid that in figures.

C. The encoding is bars, but they can be overwhelming when used excessively. Explore other options like horizontal lollipop charts in R: <https://r-graph-gallery.com/lollipop-plot.html>

D. Please color categories (bars) the same color (or use max 3 colors) and use y-axis category labels (horizontal text) to prevent readers from needing to look at the legend. Large legends are not advisable compared to directly annotating content in the chart area. Rainbow color palettes for data visualizations are not recommended.

E. When ordering categories in a plot such as this, a highest-to-lowest arrangement from top-to-bottom would enhance readability and comprehension. There are other options, but this is a good heuristic.

F. You can also gray out all vertical gridlines much more (50%+) to simplify the plot or play with removing them entirely. The 70% vertical gridline is black, whereas most others are light gray.

G. Optional, but recommended: Add a bit more padding between subplots (especially between rows of plot, perhaps 10-30% of the height of each subplot). This will create distinctions; right now, the content flows into each other too much.

H. Increase text size of plot text and numbers on axes and titles by 25-50% to see how much more readable such text can be. Text is small and blurry right now. If OK, increasing the overall size and resolution of the figure would help. I'm not sure what the publisher's restrictions are at the moment. [Editor's note: the figure only needs to fit into an A4 page.]

Response: Figure 1 has been modified to incorporate as many suggestions as possible. More specifically, the title size has been increased and to improve accuracy of the title, it now reads: " Self-admission rates of engaging in research practices at least once in their career " - graph type has been changes to lollipop - legends has been removed and the papers are now presented as y-axis labels – the title of facets are not horizontal to improve readability – the gridlines are more transparent in the new version – the text sizes have also increased to the level that avoid overlapping.

12. Conclusion: Good quotes and well-argued about an important meta-reason to support preregistrations and RR. The literature has been reviewed well and this summary is very

useful to the intended audience. I believe that the conclusion is meaningful and worth conveying.

Response: Thank you.

REVIEWER 2.

14. The part about recommendations is somewhat spread out across the article, which raises some unclearness. A clear list of recommendations, maybe with bullet points, would make the overall recommendations much more straightforward.

Response: We collected all the recommendations throughout the paper and repeated them alongside other recommendations in the section 'preregistration in practice'. To improve the readability of the section, we highlighted different recommendations by counting them in the text from line 836 onward.

15. Some of the arguments/terms used in the text might be challenging for readers without previous experience in the field, e.g. lines 614-616; I don't believe every reader will know about constructivist research and constructionist epistemology. Please try to stay away from jargon or provide small explanations for new concepts. This might be paired with the visuals recommended above.

Response: Throughout the text we have clarified terminology that readers might be less familiar with. Here specifically we now write (line 703) "such as constructivist research (which builds on the idea that knowledge about the world is always a human and social construction)"

16. Ln 550: I like the question-as-subheading technique. Can you use that approach across each subheading within major sections? That would help readers identify and use relevant subsections.

Response: Although we could change the sub-headings into questions, it feels too forced for the sub-headings where we had not already used a question. We appreciate the suggestion but we do not think it helps to identify and use sub-sections – we have used other suggestions by the reviewers to make sure the key points in the manuscripts are clear.

17. pgs. 16-32: This is a comprehensive literature review with a great deal of text. To improve navigation and skim-reading, you could add five brief tables to summarize the study types, citations, and key findings in the sections.

Response: We hope the revised manuscript and Figure 2 are sufficient to improve navigation. We acknowledge our paper is not perfect for skim-reading. It's just not that kind of review, as the level of detail and nuance is too high. But following the comments of the editor below, we believe the manuscript is now much easier to read.

18. The section on Registered Reports further highlights the need to create a unifying visual of the paper for people new to open science to situate the ideas within a whole. One suggestion is to draw out the research cycle as it is presented by the OSF with the QRPs and biases (publication bias) annotated. Then you can situate things like preregistrations, Registered Reports, and PCIRR scheduled review as interventions to correct those biases. A timeline visualization could also work if that is easier. In general, representing process-oriented information in tables and timeline visualizations could aid readers' comprehension.

Response: A diagram has been created to visualize the workflow promoted by this paper. This diagram has been added to the section "Preregistration in Practice" as an overall summary of paper.

19. Ls 416-418: PCIRR could be unpacked more for the reader. I know of it, but could foresee benefits to including more details here. Again, including that as part of the unifying visual I mentioned above would be helpful.

Response: We have added the optional step of PCI-RR to the new visual. We have also added information on PCI-RR's levels of bias in the introduction.

20. The text is still somewhat long, which is not a problem but may benefit from a form of synthesis somewhere. I would not be surprised if readers unfamiliar with the topic may get lost. Therefore, to improve this aspect, you may consider adding a box or figure:

- recapitulating the different biasing selection effects and, in parallel, how preregistration/study registries/registered reports can help reduce or prevent these effects; and/or
- explaining your vision/definition of preregistration vs study registry vs RRs (maybe combined with the point above), and/or
- highlighting terms and concepts introduced in the paper with a box containing short definitions so the readers know where to return to if they want to read that definition again instead of searching in the text. This would probably be beneficial considering that quite some terms and concepts are provided in the manuscript and that the naming of these concepts is not always universal; and/or
- showing "pro" and "cons" belief/hypotheses for preregistration

Response: We hope the improved structure, clearer definitions of key terms, and the new visual will prevent readers who are new to this topic of getting lost. We did not add a box with definitions of key terms, as we hope they are now defined clearly enough in the text, but are willing to add a box if needed.

21. Due to length and complexity of the article, attention and engagement may be dropping off before the end. A few engaging personal vignettes to reveal how preregistration and Registered Reports are experienced in your research group may be helpful. That would serve two purposes (1) engaging readers in toxicology who are new to open science and (2) clarifying how the needs and solutions work together. I recommend for each major

subsection of the paper like Preregistrations, Registered Reports, etc. adding a paragraph or two to describe cases in which metascientific problem arise in your lab(s). How will you use the technique for the goals you have? It may even be more persuasive, promoting behavior change. As there are multiple study authors, each might contribute a case if it is possible. Alternatively, you might describe a fictional researcher (in toxicology, perhaps) who seeks to verify a certain hypothesis about microplastics, lead, or something like that. Take them along a journey step-by-step to understand sources of bias, interventions like preregistration, Registered Reports, and scheduled review within PCIRR.

Response: Instead of adding one or two paragraphs of personal anecdotes to each section, we have added a description of the research process in the 'Preregistration in Practice' section, which we relate to the new Figure 2. This description and figure should be sufficient to clarify how these solutions work together, and we guide them through the different steps (open lab notebook, preregistrations, registered reported, scheduled review, etc).

22. The subsection "Misunderstanding of preregistration" should be presented earlier after initially defining the term. This is grounded in the psychology of knowledge (misinformation) revision. The evidence-based pattern to counter misconceptions is background/definitions + misconceptions + truth/consensus.

Response: Upon closer inspection, moving misunderstanding of preregistration to earlier section as specified by the reviewer, disrupts the flow of "Systematic Bias" section, where we present the definition of preregistration. However, the following sentence has been added to incorporate the evidence-based pattern as mentioned by the reviewer:

Line 197-199: "This definition also addresses many misunderstandings about the nature and implementation of preregistration, which will be discussed in the next sections."

23. Shouldn't there be a corresponding section to "Misunderstanding of preregistration" called "Misunderstandings of Registered Reports"? It seems possible this could also be important to describe. This could be a very brief section if you are dealing with time and word constraints. It could include references from literature or even personal remarks.

Response: We realize a reader might expect such a section, but there has been a surprising lack of criticism of, or misunderstandings of, Registered Reports. Indeed, critics of preregistration often intentionally ignore any discussion of Registered Reports because more problems they try to raise disappear when preregistration is implemented in a Registered Report format. For example, problems regarding a vague preregistration disappear when the preregistration is peer-reviewed during Stage 1 review. The reviewer's comment made us realize this is actually an important point to mention: Both that the best implementation of preregistration is within the Registered Report publication format, and many of the criticisms raised disappear when implemented within a Registered Report publication format.

We have added the sentence "The best implementation of preregistration is therefore in the Registered Report publication format." In the section on 'Registered Reports'.

We have also added the following sentences to the first paragraph of the ‘criticisms on preregistration’ section: “It is worth pointing out that so far there has been no published criticisms of Registered Reports, as there is widespread acknowledgement that publication bias should be prevented, and Registered Reports have the additional benefit that Stage 1 peer review can help to improve the quality of preregistrations.”

24. Lns 319-321: Explicitly define error-statistical approach to statistical inferences. Are you using a canonical term and definition or is this your own wording and definition? That is unclear right now.

Response: This comment is in line with other reviewer comments to more clearly define terminology. We have now changed the first time we mention ‘error-statistical’ in the text from “From an error-statistical approach to statistical inferences” to “From a frequentist error-statistical approach to statistical inferences (Mayo, 2018; Neyman & Pearson, 1928), which has the goal to make scientific claims based on tests that control Type 1 and 2 error rates in the long run”. We hope this clarifies that this is just the formal term for the most common approach to hypothesis testing in science, where researchers perform tests against a specific alpha level, and design the test to have sufficient statistical power.

25. Add all references that are only in the figure.

Response: All have been added.

26. You could also mention your OSF project closer to Figure 1; I had to wait until the end of the article to realise it was available. I reckon it would make more sense to mention it close to the data.

Response: The OSF link is moved closer to the figure in line 380.

27. Considering that most people only read titles and abstracts, I want to provide a useful summary so your claims can be communicated widely.

Response: We have worked on title and abstract to make them more reader friendly. See response to comments below.

28. Title: I would add a bit more detail like "The Benefits of Preregistration and Registered Reports for Testing Severely Hypotheses and Theories." Just a thought to capture relevant readers, preview the abstract, and distinguish this paper from others promoting the same practices.

Response: We considered the title, and although we focus on severely testing hypotheses, we believe our discussion is much broader. Therefore, we have kept our slightly more general title.

29. Abstract: The philosophical assumption is clearly stated, but you jump into selling a particular point of view without explaining the problem first. You can embed the falsificationist view and solution in the middle. Consider starting with the mention of research biases (their prevalence and impacts maybe even in toxicology if that is possible). You could also mention

that you are countering the dominant verificationist practices in scholarly publishing. The second sentence should also arrive in the middle. First, set the stage with concrete problems and their impacts. Then, provide a description of your review method (I believe you are using a narrative review, so that term should be included.). The last half of the abstract is sound and clear. I like this statement: "The goal of preregistration is to allow peers to transparently evaluate how severely a claim has been tested, and how the goal of Registered Reports is to reduce publication bias."

Response: We have re-written the abstract, following the reviewers' advice as much as possible. We have tried to use lay language to the best of our ability to improve readability.

30. Abstract specific suggestions:

a. Ln 29: after "science", add a comma

b. Ln 40: Remove the word "and" after "preregistration". Instead of "a review of metascientific literature," you should write "Our review of metascientific literature..." to indicate that it is referring to your review. This would clarify who is making the contribution.

c. Ln 41: "empirical support" of what?

d. Lns 42-43: "high quality" of what? Scholarship?

e. Lns 43-44: mention the general practices briefly if possible given any space constraints. If people do not read your paper, at least they will be made aware of the implications you are conveying.

Response: As per previous response, the abstract has been re-written, some of these comments are no longer relevant, others have been addressed as suggested.

31. Past and present tense are mixed early in the paper. I am OK with either option for an Introduction, but not both given your historical opening (which is nice!). I prefer past tense here.

Response: Verb tenses have been double-checked throughout the manuscript. Where appropriate the past tense has been used to improve consistency.

32. Be aware, you sometimes wrote "Registered Reports" and sometimes "Registered reports". Line 424 has one of these discrepancies occurring for instance. For consistency reason, I would recommend you stick to two capital letters.

Response: We have double-checked capitalisation and made it consistent throughout the manuscript.

33. You could go back to the opening quote and lines 53 onward and mention early it is an example of the sharpshooter fallacy so Ln 103 will be clearer.

Response: We hope our explanation of key concepts earlier in the paper has made this clearer.

34. Lns 134-36: How, for instance, would it be accomplished?

We have added the following explanation: “The most common way to demonstrate this is create the time-stamped preregistration before data is collected. Alternatively, data might already exist, but access is restricted. An example is the UK biobank where researchers need to apply for access to the data, and it is in principle possible to confirm data was not accessed before the preregistration was created. The more important it is that data provenance (when and where data were created) is trustworthy, the more researchers need to rely on electronic data capture systems, data notary services (Kleinaki et al., 2018), or independent observers that audit the data collection.”

This addition is a bit lengthy, but we feel it is important. A common concern is that people can just commit scientific fraud, and pretend to have collected the data after preregistering, when they have actually collected the data and then completed a ‘preregistration’. As with all measures to combat fraud, the research community must balance the cost of fraud against the cost of implementing procedures to prevent fraud – but these additions point readers to approaches that in principle can safeguard data provenance (even if we might not choose to implement these procedures for most preregistrations).

35. Lns 147-54: Could this be in a table for skim-reading or a simple list with numbers and text left-aligned?

Response: Following comments from both reviewers we have significantly restructured the manuscript to improve readability. The section highlighted by the reviewer – reasons to deviate from preregistration – has now been moved to section ‘Preregistration in practice’, at the end of the manuscript, which has been improved with the reader in mind and includes four recommendations to implement a good quality preregistration. Taking that into account, we feel there is no longer a need for a table.

36. Ln 160: add "to" between "necessary" and "develop"

Response: Thanks, done.

37. Line 363: should this be ‘wrote’ instead of ‘write’?

Response: We have changed ‘write’ into ‘wrote’.

38. Line 655 and Line 663: You state here, “they conclude from Study 1””observed in Study 2” – which study 1 and 2 are you referring to? Is another name supposed to be here? Also, if these are different from Collin et al. 2021, could you please add their references?

Response: We have rewritten these sentences to clarify Collins et al performed 2 studies, and that we are describing their own two 2 studies.

39. Lns 287-289: Which are the "some fields" you reference? Citations missing. Or is this meant to be hypothetical? If hypothetical, mention that and then you wouldn't need to add citations.

Response: The reviewer is completely correct that ‘for some fields’ was not a sensible addition to that sentence. We have removed these words, and now only note how for some research questions a null result is the intended outcome.

40. Lns 313-15: I believe you mean "never fully correct for publication bias" if I am interpreting you correctly. The use of “fully” would enhance clarity.

Response: Thanks for this suggestion, we agree and have added ‘fully’.

41. Lns 443-44: The sentence is a bit long. I think "...side effects of preregistration" would be more succinct.

Response: Regrettably we cannot shorten ‘potential negative side effects of preregistration’ to just ‘side effects of preregistration’ as that would suggest they exist, which we at this time do not know.

We have fixed all typo’s noted below, thanks so much for reading our manuscript so attentively.

42. Ln 534: "Criticism on Preregistration" -> "Criticism of Preregistration"

43. Ln 665: "positive" -> "positively"

44. Ln 798: "For this reasons..." should be "For this reason..."

45. Ln 805: "...,as the philosophical grounding..." should be "as well as the philosophical grounding..."

46. References: I ran the references through scite.ai and there were no significant issues like retractions.

Response: Thank you for this check – we use Zotero with the retractionwatch add-on that warns us for retractions, but we appreciate the check!

From the editor triage document:

We have completed the DOI form, but as indicated in the original manuscript, we have no conflicts of interest.

1. The article opens with an engaging quote and an interesting anecdote about Charles Babbage. However, the clarity of call to action and proposed solution could, I think, be made clearer. In particular, a more concise summary could be given up-front of how preregistration and Registered Reports achieve the (I believe) four goals of making transparent severity of tests, reduce biasing selection effects, reduce publication bias, and reduce inflation of error rates, and how these reductions are related to each other.

Response: We have added a new paragraph that contains a call to action, and make clarify earlier in the paper why readers should care about preregistration and registered reports, and now write:

“In this manuscript we will provide a state-of-the-art overview of two related solutions to reduce the negative impact of systematic bias on scientific claims: preregistration and Registered Reports. Preregistration aims to make the claim-making process more transparent. It enables peers to evaluate whether and to which extent claims were impacted by bias. Registered Reports in addition reduce publication bias, mitigating current problems in the literature where the results that are published are not representative of all studies that have been performed. Both practices help us to move towards a scientific practice where claims are severely tested: The tests we perform will prove us right when we are right, and wrong when we are wrong. We discuss when and why researchers should implement preregistration and Registered Reports with the aim to make our science more efficient and reliable.”

2. The above seems to be the central thesis of the paper. However, the authors only get to what comes across as, but may not in fact be, their primary concern (i.e. inflation of error rates in the scientific literature) by line 165. This leaves quite a long interval between being hooked into reading the paper by an interesting quote and anecdote, and the reader being told what the paper is substantially about.

Response: We hope the added paragraph directly above solves this issue.

3. I would also suggest the relationship between the issue of inflated error rates and the other central concepts of the paper (such as severity of tests and biasing selection effects) could also be further elucidated. They are clearly all of a piece, but it is not self-evident how they are related.

Response: We consider this issue part of the remarks from reviewers about clarifying key concepts and reducing jargon (point 15 by the reviewers).

4. For example, it is not clear to me on this read-through how the severity-of-test concept of the introduction sets up the point of the paper, which is to make the case for preregistration and registered reports in improving and making more transparent how severe a test is. Presenting up-front a succinct introduction to the concept of severity of test, succinct definitions and explanations of preregistration and registered reports, and then a brief overview of how the latter support the former, would help prime the reader for following the ensuing discussion.

Response: We hope the added paragraph under point 1 above, and the more extensive explanations of key concepts, achieve the desired clarifications. We are happy to include additional revisions where deemed necessary.

Strength of Argument

1. The authors' arguments definitely hit everything, but there are places where they would benefit from being more precisely targeted. (I don't mean to disparage: papers such as this are very challenging to write, and on the whole the authors have done an excellent job presenting an argument which is informative and enjoyable to read).

Response: We hope this revision achieves the desired increase in precision – we feel our argument has become clearer in response to the points raised by the reviewers.

2. It is fine to be challenging, but the balance of burden may be too much toward the reader to work through the arguments and construct the main messages of the paper. This may blunt the impact of what the authors are trying to get across, in relation to their objective of summarising the motivation and state-of-the-art for preregistration and registered reports. It will be interesting to see reviewer comments and see what the consensus ends up being for how much work should be done.

Response: We believe the reviewers provided very useful comments to improve the clarity of the paper, as well as the order in which we address topics. The additional figure hopefully helps, where we tie all key concepts together in the workflow of a scientist.

3. Echoing my comment from above, I recommend at the beginning of the paper summarising out what you are trying to achieve with it, the premises of your argument, and what you are arguing towards, so the reader knows the map of things and can then follow on your journey (rather than it being a voyage of discovery where they have to navigate their own way to the destination while simultaneously taking in the views).

Response: We hope the additional paragraph in the introduction, as well as the included figure, improve the clarity of the main points in the paper.

4. Some sections are written in a non-linear, looped discussion style where there is a tendency to state premises at the end of an argument rather than at the beginning, and to revisit more than once the idea that the authors seek to communicate, rather than front-loading the section with a clear statement of their thesis for that part of the paper. The sections from line 79 to 161, section from line 162-282, and the section line 423-533, are examples of this. The section beginning from line 623 is an example of where this issue does not seem to occur and was easier to follow.

Response: These comments (and points 5 and 6 below) mirror the detailed feedback by the editor in the annotated pdf file. We hope the changes made in response to these comments (which encompass all highlighted sections by the reviewer) also address the issues highlighted by the reviewer. We considered multi-level headings, but while attempting to incorporate this suggestion, we realized there is only 1 section (criticism on preregistration) that has multiple levels. We hope the new addition of a second figure helps in providing the direction of the argument.

5. There is also sometimes a tendency to introduce a complex idea at the end of a section as if the section has somehow explained or introduced it, when it is not clear that this is in fact the case. This leaves the idea somewhat hanging, disrupting the flow of argument as the reader is not clear what to do with it. Examples include lines 531-533, and lines 159-161. This I feel is another way in which the authors in some sections build up to the point of their argument, rather than presenting the point first and constructing the argument in its favour. The latter is much easier to follow as a reader.

Response: We agree with this comment, and it has led to several paragraphs being restructured.

6. As a more minor issue, I would also suggest the authors use numbered, multi-level headings (i.e. 1, 1.1, 1.2,.1.2.1, 1.2.2, 2, etc) to guide the reader through the structure of the manuscript. In current form, it is difficult to see where the main sections relate to subsections. The sections should also be given headings that are directly descriptive of the content of the section, so the table of contents in its own right becomes a summary of the direction of the argument.

Response: We have not done this, as these is only 1 section with subheadings, and we feel adding numbers will not improve how researchers are guided through the manuscript. We hope the new figure 2 will help to put everything together, as well as the new abstract.

Reader engagement

1. Overall, I think the article is largely written in an accessible and engaging style, though some sections are stronger in this regard than others. One issue that I think could be improved is the authors' use of jargon. I understand this type of work is jargon heavy and I have no in-principle problem with researchers inventing names for concepts when they are setting out an argument (I generally disagree that jargon should be avoided), but I think the balance in this case could be tipped more toward the reader.

Response: This is in line with point 15 by the reviewers, and addressed there.

2. Some terms, such as "biasing selection effects" I am afraid I am still not quite sure I understand. I presume the authors are trying to avoid a different term, but it is not clear which one (I think they are maybe concerned with a subcategory of the questionably-named "questionable research practices?"). Defining the term the authors are trying to avoid may allow the authors to clarify what they mean via juxtaposition.

Response: We were trying to follow the terminology in the book by Mayo (2018), not actively avoid a different term. We now simply use 'systematic bias'.

3. Similarly, making it clearer that there is more than one concept of preregistration, or that the authors wish to use the term in a way that is more narrowly focused than may be conventional, could also be helpful to the reader in following unfamiliar terminology. (EBT is in fact an example of a journal that I am sure the authors would find has a much too relaxed attitude toward preregistration. We will have a job recalibrating in response to the author's recommendations.) The way preregistration is discussed from line 123, but defined in opposition to what might be viewed as convention at line 135, without I think a sufficiently clear account of what the alternative views around what preregistration actually are, is another example of how the paper may get its message across more clearly through some careful restructuring of argument.

Response: We agree it is worth pointing out that currently everyone has a more relaxed attitude towards preregistration. This was also a topic that came up on social media in response of our preprint, and after discussion online, we believe the following clarification will be quite important (even though it adds to the length of the paper, this is a really essential and non-conventional argument that we nevertheless believe will become the standard in the future, so it is worth expanding on this).

Our definition restricts the use of the term 'preregistration' to a narrower subset of situations than is conventional. We believe this is warranted because current practice

has already started to highlight the difficulty of a less restrictive definition of preregistration. Furthermore, the definition of preregistration has already become more restrictive over time. For example, the American Psychological Association (APA) implements badges for articles that have preregistered studies. They distinguish a ‘preregistration’ badge from a ‘preregistration+’ badge, where the latter includes an analysis plan. Currently, the convention has already changed to only treat a study as preregistered when it contains an analysis plan, and Evidence-Based Toxicology also expects preregistrations to include an analysis plan (Mellor et al., 2024). Therefore, only the ‘preregistration+’ badge signals what most researchers would nowadays consider a preregistration.

Our definition restricts the use of preregistration to those studies where researchers can demonstrate that they did not have access to the data they will use to test their predictions. The APA already acknowledges that preregistrations based on existing data differ meaningfully from those created without access to the data. Whenever data already exist ‘the notation DE (Data Exist) will be added to the badge, indicating that registration postdates realization of the outcomes but predates analysis’ (American Psychological Association, 2023). Similarly, Peer Community In – Registered Reports (PCI-RR), a platform that published peer-reviews of preprints, acknowledges distinct levels of bias-control depending on whether authors had access to the data when they preregistered or not (Peer Community In - Registered Reports, n.d.). They distinguish level 6 (where data do not yet exist) and level 5 (where data exist in an access-controlled data repository and researchers can demonstrate they did not access the data) from lower levels of bias control, where authors cannot demonstrate they did not have access to the data when preregistering. Following our definition, preregistration should enable peers to transparently evaluate the severity of a test, which is not possible if the data were known to the researchers when they created their analysis plan. The strict definition of preregistration that we propose might deviate from current conventions, but this comes at the benefit of greater conceptual clarity and less confusion about how preregistration should be implemented in practice. This definition also addresses many misunderstandings about the nature and implementation of preregistration, which will be discussed in the next sections. Finally, we strongly feel that scientific practices should be justified based on principles grounded in a philosophy of science.

We propose that the ‘open lab notebook’ terminology is more appropriate for studies where data already exist. When implementing an open lab notebook researchers can log – in real time – when they first accessed data and whether and how access to the data informed their analysis plan. Preregistration and an open lab notebook approach also differ in how they control the probability of misleading claims. Where preregistration focusses on severe tests through statistical error control, in open lab notebook approaches robustness analyses, sensitivity analyses, and triangulation become more important to evaluate the severity of a test (Munafò & Smith, 2018). We recommend that researchers who have preregistered still maintain an open lab notebook. There can be good reasons why researchers need to deviate from their preregistration (Lakens, 2024), but when the main claims in a paper are based on analyses that deviated from the preregistration after seeing the data, the study should no longer be considered preregistered. It should instead be treated as an open lab notebook study, and for instance sensitivity analyses become more important.

4. In general, being generous with clear definitions of key terms and concepts especially jargon, would be helpful. I think definitions would also help the authors explain to the reader some of the interconnections between the issues they are discussing, which would help address some of the comments I make above.

Response: This is in line with point 15 by the reviewers, and addressed there.

Additional comments and suggestions for revision

1. I am not satisfied that my comments above are sufficiently constructive in relation to the structural issues that I have identified. I have therefore included an annotated copy of the manuscript to help illustrate some of the issues I have raised, and hope these are helpful to the authors. If the authors have any questions, they should arrange a call with me at their convenience to discuss my comments further.

Response: We have incorporated all detailed suggestions from the annotated PDF File, which led to the rewriting and/or restructuring of several sections. There were a lot of suggestions, but we found almost all of them points that meaningfully improved our manuscript, so we have made a number of changes to the document, which we summarize below.

In the section on ‘Systematic bias’ (previously ‘selection bias effects’) we not start with the example of switching from a two-sided to a one-sided test, and explain more carefully why this impacts the severity of the test (and what severity is). We also highlight that severity can be impacted on a theoretical, methodological, and statistical level, in line with your comments, to clarify this is not only about statistics (and we have removed any suggestion it is limited to statistics throughout the text).

We have restructured the paragraph on that bias can be introduced more or less intentionally, avoiding the non-sequitur, and more clearly explaining different sources of bias, with the goal to clarify what we mean by ‘systematic bias’. This also improves the transition from the previous paragraph, without adding any length to the paragraph.

We have clarified our definition on preregistration, and where it deviates from convention (in line with point 3 above about how our definition aligns with level 5 and 6 control-of-bias in the PCI-RR classification. We propose to refer to lower levels of bias control as ‘open lab notebook’ studies. We fully understand this is currently not the conventional way of defining preregistration. But this is mainly because current approaches to preregistration have not thought about the issues we raise sufficiently. We expect our definition to become the conventional way of distinguishing between preregistered and non-preregistered studies in the future.

The editor correctly flagged that we shifted to deviations from preregistration in the section on systematic bias. Upon reflection, we realized it made most sense to merge this paragraph with the ‘preregistration in practice’ section on deviations.

We considered changing the header ‘How biased is the scientific literature’ into the recommended header about why people should preregister – but our main point in this section is really the question how biased the scientific literature is, and whether

we know if it is seriously biased enough to warrant preregistration. So we kept the original header.

We have changed the complex single sentence comment “Some deviations do actually reduce the severity of a test, and this is the price researchers might need to pay when they decide to deviate from their preregistration.” into “However, deviating from the preregistration can in other cases increase the possibility of a Type 1 error, thereby reducing the severity of the test. For example, imagine a researcher who performs a preregistered test that yields a non-significant result. The researcher did not preregister the exclusion of outliers (even though this is best practice) but observes several outliers in their data. They decide to exclude the outliers and re-run the test. The result is now statistically significant. This non-preregistered analysis might be more valid, but the possibility that this finding is a Type 1 error has increased.”

As recommended, we have moved the discussion of research practices such as HARKing, optional stopping, and selective reporting up, before presenting Figure 1. We added a header ‘The Costs and Benefits of Preregistration’ as suggested. We moved the statement that the argument for preregistration is normative to the beginning of the first paragraph, instead of at the end. You are right that the sentence “Researchers should not preregister because it has become fashionable, is perceived as virtuous, or because the benefits are greater than the costs, but because it helps them to achieve what they believe is the goal of science.” sounds highhanded. That is indeed the impression we are trying to give. We feel it is fine to at least once in a paper reminds scientists that they are supposed to do the right thing, just because it is the right thing. We again moved the end of the paragraph to the beginning, as suggested. We changed the header ‘Metascientific evaluations of preregistration and Registered Reports’ to “The effectiveness of preregistration and Registered Reports” as suggested.

We are grateful to the editor for the many suggestions to strengthen the write-up of our paper, and we believe these suggestions have substantially improved our manuscript.

2. Figure 1 needs revision for readability. Making the bars vertical and legends horizontal will be more readable. The order of studies in the legend should be the same as the order in the charts. Numbering the studies in the legend and numbering the bars will also help with associating a bar with a study.

Response: This is addressed as part of comment 11 by the reviewers.

3. I wonder (line 135) if the authors’ definition of preregistration is likely to be highly contentious, because it means systematic reviews cannot be preregistered? This seems sufficiently far out of step with convention that the definition could seem not to be credible. It also seems to be inconsistent with PCI-RR as a community that has a major role in normalising preregistration as an activity. Clearly presenting the differences in views as what preregistration ought to be seems very important here.

Response: This point is similar to, and refers to the same lines of text, as point 3 under ‘reader engagement’. In our response there, we do not address the point that systematic review also do not fall under ‘preregistration’. We believe it should be possible to preregister systematic reviews (and have argued for this in the past (Lakens et al., 2016)) but indeed, if researchers have extensive knowledge of the literature to the point that they would already know with a high probability what certain analyses will reveal, the same issues as we raise here come into play. We believe future meta-scientific research is needed to inform us about how plausible preregistration of systematic reviews is – there is currently not enough information to make a strong statement about this.

4. This is more of a point of observation about our own policies at EBT around preregistration rather than a comment authors need to respond to. At EBT we have seven preregistration categories, adapted from PCI-RR, to allow us to explain the extent to which a study is preregistered rather than set a threshold for what counts as a preregistration. Our definition is based on process rather than concept (so I disagree that it is sufficient that a definition be based on a philosophy of science - sometimes, a definition needs to be operationalisable), whereby preregistration is the act of registering a time-stamped, third-party-controlled record of planned methods prior to collection of data. As an editor, I think this keeps things very simple, whereas I would find it challenging to interpret your definition into policy.

Response: We understand that in practice there is a difference in the implementation of preregistration, or Registered Reports, and our definition of preregistration. Building on point 3 under reader engagement, we do not believe it should be challenging to implement our definition into policy. Our recommendations are as follows:

1. Distinguish between preregistered studies (where researchers can demonstrate they did not have access to the data – level 5 and 6 in the current PCI-RR Table 1 https://rr.peercommunityin.org/about/full_policies#h_95790490510491613309490336) and open lab notebook studies (where researchers transparently document when and how they interacted with a dataset, levels 1 to 4 in the current PCI-RR Table). Our main disagreement with Table 1 is that we do not allow authors to ‘certify’ that they did not look at the data.

2. Treat any preregistered studies with extensive deviations from the preregistration as an open lab notebook study.

3. Stress Type 1 and 2 error control or preregistered studies that test hypotheses. Stress robustness and sensitivity analyses, and/or triangulation, for open lab notebook studies.

Our recommendation is actually already aligned with PCI-RR policy, as it allows journals to set a minimum required level of bias control to protect against prior data observation (https://rr.peercommunityin.org/about/pci_rr_friendly_journals). Our recommendation therefore boils down to only accept studies in level 5 or 6 for publication as preregistered studies. Studies at lower levels of bias control can of course also be considered for publication in a different article category, such as an open lab notebook study.

5. Line 337 might be overstating the role that editorial statements have in changing research practices. Quite often they don’t (PRISMA endorsement being a notorious example), and probably change in law was more important, see e.g. Zarin et al. (2019).

Response: Thank you for this interesting reference. We completely agree that our write up made it sound as if a law-case and editorial policies were enough – you are correct NIH policies were probably the main driver. We have added: “Subsequent regulations and policies of the NIH provided an important impetus for the widespread adoption of trial registration (Zarin et al., 2019).”

6. Line 401: I think the reviewers for registered reports check not only the conclusion, but the extent to which the researchers adhered to their planned methods, the reasonableness of deviation from those methods, and the validity of interpretation of the evidence in findings and conclusions?

Response: You are completely right. We now write: “Now that the manuscript includes the results and the conclusions reviewers check the extent to which the researchers followed their preregistration, evaluate the consequences of any deviations from the preregistration in terms of the severity and validity of the tests (Lakens, 2024), and check whether the conclusions follow from the data.”

7. Line 416: I think there may be a conflation of two functions of PCI RR. Scheduling and PCI are very different things - at EBT, we can schedule the review of submissions to speed along the process, and have nothing to do with PCI at all. PCI itself is an intervention designed to disconnect peer-review from journals, which is independent of scheduling (or even registered reports itself).

Response: We agree our write up conflated scheduled review and PCI-RR. We now discuss scheduled review on it’s own, then we note that PCI-RR is one example of where this has been implemented, and we note that Evidence Based Toxicology will publish manuscripts reviews by PCI-RR.